

Volumetric and ultrasonic studies of molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures of styrene with toluene at different temperatures

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Abstract : This paper presents experimental data for densities (ρ) and ultrasonic speeds (u) of pure styrene and toluene and of their binary liquid mixtures over the entire composition range at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. From the experimental data the excess molar volumes (V^E), deviations in isentropic compressibilities (Δk_s), and in acoustic impedances (ΔZ), were calculated for the binary mixtures over the entire composition range at all the temperatures. Moreover, partial molar volumes, $V_{\phi,1}^0$ and $V_{\phi,2}^0$ and partial molar isentropic compressibilities, $K_{\phi,1}^0$ and $K_{\phi,2}^0$ at infinite dilution of styrene in toluene and toluene in styrene were examined. The variations of these parameters with composition of mixture suggest the strength of interactions between the component molecules under study.

Keywords : Densities, ultrasonic speeds, thermodynamic properties, intermolecular interactions, binary mixtures.

Introduction

The studies of volumetric and ultrasonic properties of liquid mixtures and their dependence on composition and temperature are of great significance in many fields of applied research and find applications in many important chemical, industrial and biological processes¹⁻⁵. The possible change in these properties and the degree of deviation from ideality has been found to be an excellent qualitative and quantitative way to obtain the information regarding the molecular structure and intermolecular interactions^{6,7}. The mixtures of styrene with toluene are very interesting both from the experimental as well as theoretical point of view, because toluene, a non-polar and aprotic molecule (used as an excellent solvent for blending of petrol, paints, resins and rubber, as a starting material for benzyl derivatives, benzoic acid and benzaldehyde), is mixed with styrene which is a rigid plate like molecule containing an olefinic chain attached to an aromatic ring. It is stabilized by dipole-dipole interactions and is an important industrial monomer used in large scale preparation of various polymers⁸.

Very recently densities, viscosities and ultrasonic speeds for binary mixtures of anisole with *m*-, *o*- or *p*-

xylene, toluene and mesitylene were reported by Jasem *et al.*⁹. To the best of our knowledge, no volumetric and ultrasonic studies have been reported for the binary mixtures of styrene with toluene, except the work of Peralta *et al.*¹⁰ who studied only excess molar volume of binary mixtures of styrene with toluene at 298.15 K.

We have measured the densities (ρ) and ultrasonic speeds (u) of pure styrene and toluene and those of their binary mixtures over the entire composition range at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. The above experimental data were used to evaluate the excess molar volumes (V^E), deviations in isentropic compressibilities (Δk_s), and in acoustic impedances (ΔZ) at each temperature. All of these excess and deviation quantities have been fitted to Redlich and Kister type polynomial equation¹¹. Moreover, the apparent molar volume, $V_{\phi,1}$ and $V_{\phi,2}$, apparent molar compressibility, $K_{\phi,1}$ and $K_{\phi,2}$ and partial molar volume, $V_{\phi,1}^0$ and $V_{\phi,2}^0$ and partial molar compressibility, $K_{\phi,1}^0$ and $K_{\phi,2}^0$ of styrene in toluene and toluene in styrene at infinite dilution, have also been calculated. These derived parameters are found to be quite sensitive towards the interactions present in a mixture.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of densities (ρ) and ultrasonic speeds (u) of pure styrene, toluene and of their nine binary mixtures as a function of mole fraction (x_1) of styrene at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K are listed in Table 1. From Table 1 it is clear that density as well as ultrasonic speed increase as the concentration of styrene

Table 1. Experimental densities (ρ) and ultrasonic speeds (u) of binary liquid mixtures styrene + toluene at different temperatures

x_1	ρ (kg m ⁻³)			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
0.0000	862.1	857.6	853.2	848.7
0.1148	867.2	862.7	858.3	853.9
0.2116	871.4	867.0	862.5	858.1
0.3030	875.3	870.9	866.3	861.9
0.3999	879.3	874.9	870.3	865.9
0.5156	884.2	879.5	874.8	870.4
0.5976	887.2	882.7	878.0	873.6
0.7070	891.3	886.8	882.1	877.6
0.8028	894.8	890.3	885.5	881.0
0.9124	898.7	894.1	889.2	884.6
1.0000	901.8	897.1	892.0	887.3
x_1	u (m s ⁻¹)			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
0.0000	1304.0	1288.5	1274.8	1247.8
0.1148	1317.2	1302.2	1288.6	1263.9
0.2116	1328.2	1312.2	1298.0	1273.7
0.3030	1337.6	1320.8	1305.6	1281.0
0.3999	1346.6	1329.0	1312.0	1287.6
0.5156	1355.6	1337.2	1318.7	1294.5
0.5976	1360.9	1342.0	1322.6	1298.8
0.7070	1367.6	1348.0	1327.2	1303.7
0.8028	1372.6	1352.0	1330.0	1306.5
0.9124	1378.0	1356.0	1332.0	1308.0
1.0000	1383.0	1360.0	1334.0	1309.0

in the mixture increases. This may be attributed to the increased interaction between styrene and toluene molecules in the mixture. In order to have an insight into the interactions between the component molecules of the mixture, the values of excess molar volumes (V^E), deviations in isentropic compressibilities (Δk_s), and in acoustic impedances (ΔZ), were calculated with the help of following standard relations :

$$V^E = V - (x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta k_s = k_s - (\phi_1 k_{s1} + \phi_2 k_{s2}) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta Z = Z - (x_1 Z_1 + x_2 Z_2) \quad (3)$$

where x and ϕ are the mole fraction and volume fraction, respectively. Subscripts 1 and 2 stand for the pure components styrene and toluene, respectively, V , k_s and Z are the molar volume, isentropic compressibility and acoustic impedance of the mixture and can be evaluated by the following relations :

$$V = (x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2) / \rho \quad (4)$$

$$k_s = 1 / u^2 \rho \quad (5)$$

$$Z = u \rho \quad (6)$$

where M is the molar mass of the pure components. The values of excess and deviation functions V^E , Δk_s and ΔZ were fitted to Redlich and Kister type equation¹¹ :

$$Y^E = x_1 x_2 \sum_{i=1}^5 A_i (1 - 2x_1)^{i-1} \quad (7)$$

where Y^E stands for V^E or Δk_s or ΔZ , A_i are the polynomial coefficients, and x_2 is the mole fraction of component 2, i.e. toluene. The coefficients A_i , obtained by the method of least-squares with all points being given equal weightage, together with the standard deviations $\sigma(Y^E)$, calculated as,

$$\sigma(Y^E) = [\sum (Y^E_{\text{expt}} - Y^E_{\text{cal}})^2 / (m - k)]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

where m is the number of experimental data points and k is the number of A_i coefficients considered and have been listed in Table 2. The small values of standard deviations, $\sigma(Y^E)$, Table 2, suggest the applicability of the polynomial eq. (7) in reproducing the experimental results of the systems investigated. The smooth values of V^E , Δk_s and ΔZ , obtained by using eq. (7), as a function of mole fraction x_1 , of styrene are graphically presented in Figs. 1-3.

It is clear from Figs. 1 and 2 that the values of both V^E and Δk_s are negative over the entire composition range at all the four temperatures under study. An explanation for the behaviour of V^E and Δk_s with the composition of the mixture may be given by considering the order in the pure liquids and in the solution and also by considering the interactions between the component molecules in the mixtures. When a rigid plate like styrene molecule is mixed with toluene which is structurally considered as the homomorph of methyl cyclohexane, aprotic and almost nonpolar molecule, the order is destroyed because styrene has an order breaking ability¹². This would cause an expansion in volume, thereby, positive V^E and Δk_s are expected. But, because of the interstitial accommodation of the component molecules into each other's structure

Table 2. Coefficients A_i of eq. (7) along with the standard deviations, $\sigma(Y^E)$

T (K)	A_1	A_2	A_3 V^E (10^{-8} m ³ mol ⁻¹)	A_4	A_5	$\sigma(Y^E)$
298.15	-33.1304	6.2544	8.6466	-10.4476	2.7837	0.0567
303.15	-40.4345	5.4104	2.2722	-4.0768	11.3266	0.0515
308.15	-45.1285	9.7547	-23.977	1.9382	24.4379	0.0146
313.15	-55.2591	10.7663	-22.4902	-1.4148	10.6645	0.0732
			Δk_s (10^{-11} m ² N ⁻¹)			
298.15	-4.7473	-1.5361	0.7027	0.4268	1.2345	0.0079
303.15	-5.2825	-1.2352	-0.1349	-1.1635	1.1548	0.0080
308.15	-6.0557	-1.5360	-2.1551	-1.2085	2.4282	0.0080
313.15	-7.3102	-1.4235	-3.7975	-2.7896	1.7797	0.0043
			ΔZ (10^3 kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)			
298.15	43.0333	8.5149	-9.3703	-1.6068	-11.4774	0.0768
303.15	47.0129	5.0799	-0.5367	11.4104	-12.6204	0.0730
308.15	53.0497	6.9211	17.8822	9.7428	-23.7350	0.0679
313.15	59.7246	4.1989	29.9312	20.0388	-18.1745	0.0289

Fig. 2. Plots of deviations in isentropic compressibilities Δk_s against mole fraction x_1 of styrene for the binary mixtures at 298.15 K (●), 303.15 K (○), 308.15 K (▲) and 313.15 K (◐).

and also due to the possible $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction between π -electrons of benzene ring of styrene and that of toluene, there will be contraction in volume of the solution. Thus, the observed negative V^E and Δk_s values for the mixtures suggest the dominance of the $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction between the styrene and toluene molecules and also due to the favourable accommodation of the component molecules into each other's structure. This is in accordance with the view proposed by Fort and Moore¹³, that V^E and Δk_s become increasingly negative as the strength of interac-

tion between the unlike molecules increases and also due to fitting of component molecules of different molecular size into each other's structure.

The values of ΔZ (Fig. 3) show positive deviations, which indicate the presence of significant interactions between the component molecules in the binary liquid mixtures. The estimated positive deviations in ΔZ , where $Z = u\rho$, and an opposite trend in Δk_s , where $k_s = 1/(u^2\rho)$, Fig. 2 over the whole composition range support our

Fig. 3. Plots of deviations in acoustic impedances ΔZ against mole fraction x_1 of styrene for the binary mixtures at 298.15 K (\circ), 303.15 K (\square), 308.15 K (\blacktriangle) and 313.15 K (\diamond).

view regarding the structural order and, hence, intermolecular interactions in these mixtures. Similar conclusion regarding the ΔZ values were also drawn by Ali *et al.*¹⁴ for styrene + *m*-, *o*-, or *p*-xylene binary mixtures.

Furthermore, the extent of interactions between the component molecules in a mixture is well reflected in the parameters like apparent molar volumes, apparent molar compressibilities, partial molar volumes and partial molar compressibilities^{15,16}. The apparent molar volumes, $V_{\phi,1}$ and $V_{\phi,2}$ of styrene in toluene and of toluene in styrene, respectively, were calculated by using the relations reported by Pal and co-workers¹⁷.

$$V_{\phi,1} = V_1^* + (V^E/x_1) \quad (9)$$

$$V_{\phi,2} = V_2^* + (V^E/x_2) \quad (10)$$

where V_1^* and V_2^* are the molar volumes of styrene and toluene, respectively. The partial molar volumes, $V_{\phi,1}^0$ and $V_{\phi,2}^0$ of styrene and toluene at infinite dilution were obtained by using the method described in the literature^{14,15}. The deviations in $V_{\phi,1}^0$ and $V_{\phi,2}^0$ at infinite dilution, ΔV_1 and ΔV_2 were calculated using the following relation¹⁵ :

$$\Delta V_1 = V_{\phi,1}^0 - V_1^* \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta V_2 = V_{\phi,2}^0 - V_2^* \quad (12)$$

The values of $V_{\phi,1}^0$, $V_{\phi,2}^0$, V_1^* , V_2^* , ΔV_1 and ΔV_2 are listed in Table 3. It is clear from Table 3 that $V_{\phi,1}^0$ and $V_{\phi,2}^0$ values are smaller than the corresponding molar volumes V_1^* and V_2^* , leading to negative ΔV_1 and ΔV_2 , values which are indicative of contraction in volume of the mixtures. This, in turn, suggests the presence of appreciable interactions between the component molecules under study.

The apparent molar compressibilities, $K_{\phi,1}$ of styrene in toluene and $K_{\phi,2}$ of toluene in styrene were calculated using the relation¹⁵ :

$$K_{\phi,1} = (k_s V)^E/x_1 + K_{\phi,1}^* \quad (13)$$

$$K_{\phi,2} = (k_s V)^E/x_2 + K_{\phi,2}^* \quad (14)$$

where $(k_s V)^E$ is the excess molar compressibility of the mixture and $K_{\phi,1}^*$ and $K_{\phi,2}^*$ are the molar isentropic compressibility of styrene and toluene, respectively. The partial molar compressibilities $K_{\phi,1}^0$ and $K_{\phi,2}^0$ of styrene and toluene at infinite dilution were obtained by the procedure given in the literature^{14,15}. The deviations in $K_{\phi,1}^0$ and $K_{\phi,2}^0$ at infinite dilution, ΔK_1 and ΔK_2 were obtained using the relations¹⁵ :

$$\Delta K_1 = K_{\phi,1}^0 - K_{\phi,1}^* \quad (15)$$

Table 3. Values of $V_{\phi,1}^0$, $V_{\phi,2}^0$, V_1^* , V_2^* , ΔV_1 , ΔV_2 , $K_{\phi,1}^0$, $K_{\phi,2}^0$, $K_{\phi,1}^*$, $K_{\phi,2}^*$, ΔK_1 and ΔK_2 for the binary mixtures at different temperatures

T (K)	$V_{\phi,1}^0$	V_1^*	ΔV_1	$V_{\phi,2}^0$	V_2^*	ΔV_2
			$(10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1})$			
298.15	1.1547	1.1549	-0.2097	1.0658	1.0688	-2.9458
303.15	1.1607	1.1610	-0.2726	1.0705	1.0744	-3.8448
308.15	1.1672	1.1676	-0.3687	1.0745	1.0799	-5.4598
313.15	1.1735	1.1738	-0.3299	1.0789	1.0857	-6.7183
	$K_{\phi,1}^0$	$K_{\phi,1}^*$	ΔK_1	$K_{\phi,2}^0$	$K_{\phi,2}^*$	ΔK_2
			$(10^{-4} \text{ m}^5 \text{ N}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1})$			
298.15	6.7136	6.6957	0.0178	6.8971	7.2908	-0.3937
303.15	7.0339	6.9968	0.0371	7.0808	7.5458	-0.4650
308.15	7.4125	7.3556	0.0568	7.1897	7.7886	-0.5982
313.15	7.8123	7.7204	0.0919	7.4218	8.2158	-0.7939

$$\Delta K_2 = K_{\phi,2}^0 - K_{\phi,2}^* \quad (16)$$

The values $K_{\phi,1}^0$, $K_{\phi,2}^0$, $K_{\phi,1}^*$, $K_{\phi,2}^*$, ΔK_1 and ΔK_2 are included in Table 3. The K_{ϕ}^0 values characterize the compressibility of the component molecules in the mixture, whereas, the molar isentropic compressibility K_{ϕ}^* of a pure component can be considered as its partial molar compressibility when dissolved in itself. Table 3 reveals that deviations in ΔK_1 are small positive whereas ΔK_2 are negative, suggesting the presence of appreciable molecular interactions between the components in the system under study. This further supports our earlier findings. Thus, the variations of V^E , Δk_s , ΔZ , ΔV_i and ΔK_i truly complement each other in describing the behaviours of the present binary liquid mixtures.

Experimental

Styrene (Acros, 99%) and toluene (Qualigens, 99%) were purified according to the standard procedures¹⁸. The mixtures were prepared by mass in a dry box and kept in special air tight bottles. The weighing were done on an electronic balance Afcoset ER-120A with a precision of ± 0.1 mg.

The densities of pure liquids and their binary mixtures were measured by using a single-capillary pycnometer, made of Borosil glass having a bulb capacity of 8×10^{-6} m³. The capillary with graduated marks had a uniform bore and could be closed by a well-fitted glass cap. The marks on the capillary were calibrated by using triple distilled water. The ultrasonic speeds were measured using a single-crystal variable path ultrasonic interferometer operating at 2 MHz as described in literature¹⁹⁻²¹. The accuracies of the density and ultrasonic speed measurements were ascertained by comparing the experimental values for pure liquids with the literature values²²⁻²⁴ at 298.15 K in Table 4. The temperature of the test liquids and their binary mixtures were maintained to an accuracy of ± 0.02 K in an electronically controlled thermostatic water bath.

Table 4. Comparison of measured densities and ultrasonic speeds of pure components with literature values at 298.15 K

Component	ρ (kg m ⁻³)		u (m s ⁻¹)	
	Experimental	Literature	Experimental	Literature
Toluene	862.8	862.6 ²²	1304.0	1304.3 ²²
Styrene	901.8	902.3 ²³	1383.0	1390.0 ²⁴

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